

An application oriented IoT based real-time livestock management system using machine learning technology in secure manner

Salman Us Sakib
Institute of Information Technology
Jahangirnagar University
Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Email: sakeebalsalman1@gmail.com

Sabbir Ahmed
Institute of Information Technology
Jahangirnagar University
Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Email: sabbir.iit.ju@gmail.com

MD. Uthba Bin Anowar Binoy
Institute of Information Technology
Jahangirnagar University
Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Email: binoyanowar@gmail.com

Sweet Rana
Institute of Information Technology
Jahangirnagar University
Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Email: ashikex49@gmail.com

Rashed Mazumder
Institute of Information Technology
Jahangirnagar University
Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Email: rakhu345@yahoo.com

Abstract—The livestock monitoring and prediction system is composed of several components. To begin, a multi-sensory device should be developed to collect all of the required physiological data from farm animals. The sensing device will be minimally processed and networked. Such IoT solutions will provide all of the data necessary for the back-end application to function properly. Hence, the second component of the system is an edge-cloud storage solution for securely communicating and storing data. The edge-cloud computing architecture redistributes processing power, resulting in faster computing. Moreover, AES based encryption is used at the network's edge to prevent intrusion. A software defined network (SDN) for validating the packets sent by the edge device can significantly improve security. The cloud system contained the necessary decryption procedures to convert the data to a suitable format. Following that, the third component of the system consists of both traditional deterministic and machine learning-related probabilistic algorithms, as well as pre-processing of the IoT system's collected data. Machine learning algorithms will be used to monitor and forecast strategies such as health conditions, meat production, milk production, and pregnancy prediction, among others.

Index Terms—Livestock Monitoring System, Health monitoring, IoT, Cloud Computing, Sensor, Neural Network

I. INTRODUCTION

In the modern world, everything is now based upon technology. Without using technology, there will be no such progress in any field of work, including farming practices. In past years, farming was fully dependent upon farmers' experience and environment. But from the last three or four decades, we can see that farmers are not only relying on their farming skills, they are trying to use modern technologies to improve their farming practices. For that, LMS (Livestock Monitoring System) has been introduced to modern farming techniques for the betterment of animal-based production. The Livestock Monitoring System has so many features like monitoring of

animal health, disease, daily milk production, meat consumption, pregnancy prediction, regular vaccination. From these features, farmers can easily observe the current situation of the animal and from that, they categorize their further steps to avoid harmful factors. Physiological factors are deeply related to livestock monitoring. Health welfare and milk production can be predicted more accurately by analyzing physiological factors such as head movement, movement velocity, grazing time, etc. Time spent lying, standing plays an important role to predict milk production. By utilizing the previous data about physiological factors owners can be benefited increasing milk production and health welfare. In traditional livestock farming, farmers use their total time with their livestock. But in the modern farming system, they don't have to spend time with them. They can use technologies to monitor them. The Livestock Monitoring System reduces all the demerits of traditional farming. Traditional farming causes many problems as the farmers are not aware of any condition of the animal-like health issues, pregnancy report, vaccination date, milk production ratio, etc. If they were aware of these situations, they could easily prevent animal sickness. That's why traditional systems are backdated in farming. Without modern technology, no such progress is possible in the livestock farming industry.

Animal production will decrease day by day if we stick with traditional techniques. Monitoring systems and physiological factors play a significant role in farming cattle. By monitoring the physiological factors owners could be able to improve animal health conditions. Analyzing the previous data-set about physiological factors it's possible to decide whether animals are healthy or not and further steps can be taken. Predicting the production of milk is another important role that is played by the monitoring system. According to the demand of the market, the owner can utilize his prediction result and

can be benefited. Nowadays, sensing technology is widely used in the livestock monitoring system. Various sensors are used in the monitoring system to collect the required information. This information is used to monitor animal behavior as well as their physiological factors such as movement, body temperature, grazing time, etc. Global Positioning System(GPS) is used to calculate the total grazing time [1], [2]. To monitor the movement of livestock and measure soil moisture static WSNs are used. On the other hand, mobile WSNs are used to measure body temperature, health condition, and behavior. Besides, radio frequency identification(RFID), another type of sensor which is used to monitor and track the cattle [3].

Sensing technology helps to extract accurate information and made monitoring systems easier. IoT, the Internet of Things plays a vital role in livestock monitoring systems. From sensors, we collect physical data of the animals. We get many kinds of data from sensors, electrical devices like body temperature, heart bit rate, etc. IoT-based sensors are connected with the Cloud Computing system. These data are equipped with the sensors and it connects the real world to the virtual world. Predictive models or Artificial Intelligence algorithms can process these data and store them in the Cloud. From that, we can generate new insights into that information and this helps to predict future decision making. Day-to-day data stored in the cloud and from that data set, we get to know the condition of an animal's health, milk production, meat consumption, pregnancy period, etc. Machine Learning(ML) is sub-field of Artificial Intelligence [4]. Nowadays, Machine Learning is widely used in livestock farming in monitoring and prediction. Using various sensors, dairy farmers can collect a huge amount of data, and later they can use this data-set to monitor the health of animals. They can also predict the production of milk using a large data set.

In traditional statistical models, monitoring and prediction are done by certain theories but in the ML model, it is done based on a real data-set that is previously collected [?]. So, livestock farmers are able to monitor perfectly and predict more accurately using machine learning in the livestock monitoring system. Internet of Things(IoT) is a system where a smart device can transfer data over a communication network. Machine learning and IoT brought a tremendous revolution in the business sector. Using the IoT, huge amounts of data can be collected. This data-set can be utilized perfectly by using ML algorithms to predict the upcoming scenarios in business insights. Businessmen can analyze the data which was previously collected and make the right decision to make the best profit.

II. BACKGROUND STUDY

Sensing technology enables ubiquitous measurements of various physiological aspects of livestock. Visual object tracking, a crucial approach, is used to create intelligent livestock management systems. Important information about breeding and health may be gleaned from animal behavioural patterns. Kim et al. [5] provided a basic thermal frame threshold being a topographical face as the definition boundary of an

object works also well in overlapping situations. All animals' placements are regularly updated using an effective refining method based on their separation as a consequence of structural manipulations on the topology. Hence, it is robust to the animals' abrupt movements. This thermal sensor based camera technology assists for multiple object tracking. Though, thermal camera system use heavy computational effort and can create network congestion in IoT. In another work, the authors [6] investigates the potential solutions for welfare quality assessment methods based on sensor data. PLF technology could be enhanced in a number of areas. These are described in this article. For dairy cattle, the welfare quality protocol has 4 principles, 12 criteria, and 31 metrics. Comfort when sleeping, the absence of discomfort caused by treatment approaches, and a healthy human-animal relationship are some of the prerequisites for sustainable ML solutions. ML systems can be enhanced in the field of social behavior expression. One of the most significant aspects of livestock management is detecting estrus, the time when insemination occurs. Accuracy in recognizing estrus boosts output and profits. L. Mattias Andersson [7] proposed a intravaginal wireless probe which is able to detect estrus in a farm.

It is difficult and expensive to use traditional methods to detect estrus. This wireless technology simplifies the estrus detection process. Functionality and dependability have yet to be demonstrated on a broader scale. Germani et al. [8] proposed a LoRa (LPWAN) based solution covering the various settings and a web services setup for continual animal surveillance, processing and analysis in farms and grasslands. They performed range performance, battery lifespan and accuracy analyses of the architectures with experimental 7 km of range, reduced required power and multi gateway multi device connectivity. Although Low bit rate data transfer up to 27 kbps are not applicable for all types of sensors. Similarly Abou et al. [9] suggested adhoc on demand distance vector routing (AODV) with power efficiency for livestock IoT application. By simulating both power gain and transmitted power, their proposed AODV showed reduced energy drain. Real time field test for cattle monitoring is missing in this article. Real time field tests has a significant impact on the networking and IoT solutions. Beng et al. [10] experimented with wireless power transfer(WPT), NFC and WSN for livestock IoT devices which solve the recharging issues.

A wireless power transfer system that uses radio frequency energy to power distant wireless power transfer devices connected to the animal. Whereas the WSN and NFC enables connection to the internet. The power transmission wattage and WSN architecture has not been mentioned. Numerous studies have been undertaken in the area of livestock monitoring using remote sensor and Internet of Things (IoT) technologies. Vigneswari et al. [11] surveyed several IoT based monitoring and management systems with devices attached to the livestock. The fundamental disadvantages of surveyed systems are higher energy consumption, difficult designs, interfaces, and high installation and maintenance costs, which continue to make farmers' adaptation of these smart systems problematic.

Zeng et al. [12] designed external sixteen channel wireless multi sensor PCB devices to capture information like wind speed, temperature, barometric pressure, light intensity, rain, humidity, wind direction and gas amount.

Previously few approaches have been taken to address this issue. Rosa raghi et al. [13] introduced by Moo-Care, a paradigm for assisting farmers with dairy farm management. Their solution used IoT based milk supply predictions to boost agricultural output. The build of milk production and feed sensor does not explained, private data set, thus results can not be validated. Another approach has been taken by Faruq et al. [14]. They combined monitoring systems and detection systems under a banner using IoT and intelligent system. They have achieved 90 percent accuracy for different disease detection. They only used heart rate and temperature sensor, which excludes many vital sensing data. IoT paired with AI visualizes statistics about the cattle’s activity, such as mealtime, milk color, and amount of milk [15]. Smart collar design with capabilities for internet activity can also be used to monitor body temperature, heart rate, blood pressure which will give important insights about the cattle well being and management systems [16]. High power consumption, no sustainable power source, and lack of security are some of the drawbacks of this study.

III. METHODOLOGY

Fig. 1. Workflow for The Proposed Livestock Monitoring and Prediction System.

The livestock monitoring and prediction system is separated into several parts. First, a multi-sensory device has to be developed in order to collect all the necessary physiological aspects of farm animals. These aspects include but are not limited to body temperature, heart rate variability, sudden movement and acceleration, food consumption, respiration rate, rumination, heartbeat, heat stress, blood pressure, physical gesture, humidity, which are embedded in a single device

like system. This device will be implemented with minor processing and networking capabilities. External factors such as location tracking, herd management, gazing time for accurate livestock monitoring will be implemented in separate devices and will work as a part of the farming system. The devices mentioned above will connect to the cloud with supported protocols like MQTT, TCP/IP, and CoAP. These IoT solutions will provide all the necessary information required for the back-end application to be operational. Figure 4 delineate the message passing sequence diagram of proposed system. Thus,

Fig. 2. Use cases for The Proposed Livestock Monitoring and Prediction System.

the second part of the system consists of a cloud storage solution for storing the data securely. As the sensors are coupled with a microprocessor or micro-controller with limited computational power, some pre-processing will reduce the workload at the server end. AES and other layerwise security measures will be taken to ensure security [17]. This cloud-edge computing scheme will redistribute the total amount of processing resulting in faster computing. After that, the third part of the system comprises both traditional deterministic and ML-related probabilistic algorithms with pre-processing of the collected data by the IoT system. Figure 1 describe the activity diagram of proposed system. The deterministic algorithm will be utilized to calculate definitive decisions like time of vaccination, number of animals in one cattle, cattle management, the energy efficiency of the firm, and many more. ML algorithms will be involved in monitoring and predicting strategies like health conditions, meat production, milk production, pregnancy prediction, etc. To predict from the numerical pre-processed data, ML classifiers like SVM, RF, ANN will be utilized. For the prediction from historical data, time series analysis deep learning algorithms such as RNN, LSTM will be utilized. However, it should be mentioned that the most appropriate and accurate algorithm will be implemented in the final application among the algorithms. For the last part of the LMS system, both mobile and web platform applications will be developed for friendly user- interaction

and usability. Figure 1 depicts the block view of proposed system.

A. IoT and Cloud Networking

Fig. 3. Activity diagram of Livestock Monitoring and Prediction System.

B. Sensors

DHT11: The DHT11 is a simple digital humidity and temperature sensor. To measure the ambient air, it employs a sensitive thermostat. It outputs serial data. Then sequential digital signal can be converted into numbers and text that correspond to the actual temperature value in celsius and percentage of humidity in the air. Furthermore, we will use the sensor of MLX90614, KG011, GY-25, and ADXL335.

RR sensor based system: This system is made of three components. First of all, it has a respiratory rate sensor and a belt covering the animal's body. It captures the whole body of the animal and measures the respiration rate. Then a device is set to collect data from the sensors to calculate the respiration rate [18]

C. IoT and Cloud Networking

IoT and Cloud are collaborating in livestock monitoring systems to sense and predict data. IoT refers to the Internet of Things is implanted with sensors, software, etc., to connect and exchange data from various devices, and then it connects these data to the internet. On the other hand, cloud computing is used for storing these data in a database that

is connected to the internet. Cloud has different types of servers, databases, software which are used for storing data in a remote database. These data have been saved as files, and anybody can retrieve the saved files whenever they want. In livestock monitoring, the animal's monitored data can be collected by IoT-based systems, and then it has been stored in the Cloud for surveying the data to make decisions.

IoT has several protocols that connect the devices to the cloud. Below are some of these few protocols :

MQTT: This is an underlying communication protocol. It stands for MQ Telemetry Platform. It works efficiently in low bandwidth environments. It distributes telemetry information as it is an open messaging protocol.

CoAP: It stands for Constrained Application Protocol that is a customized web transfer protocol for usage with embedded devices and limited networks. CoAP is a protocol that enables basic, limited devices to connect with the Internet of Things, even when bandwidth and availability are limited.

D. ML based Prediction

ML-based prediction normally follows two kinds of algorithms. One is deterministic and another one is a probabilistic algorithm.

Deterministic Algorithm: This algorithm always has static input and generates the same output in any situation. Here, the machine generally passes via the same state sequences. On the whole, we can say that this algorithm has always a predefined output. In this article, we certainly wish to collect and analyze definitive data like identifying specific animals, number of animals in one cattle, vaccination period, cattle management, etc by using this deterministic type of algorithm.

Probabilistic Algorithm: This algorithm mainly follows a statistical technique for predicting for estimating the likelihood of future events while accounting for the impact of random events or actions. This process can work on random data where a deterministic algorithm has the limitation of it. In our proposed work, we can use this algorithm to predict health conditions, daily milk production rate, animal pregnancy cycle, etc. For this, we wish to use some ML classifiers, such as:

SVM: Support Vector Machine (SVM) is a ML approach by predicting initial points. It uses a trick called the kernel trick. This can alter the data and uses these adjustments to identify the optimal border between the various outputs. It normally creates a line that divides data into different classes.

ANN: Artificial Neural Network depends on machine learning algorithm. In addition, it is worked as human neurons. This model is designed based on human neurons.

Fig. 4. Sequence diagram of Livestock Monitoring and Prediction System.

It has a huge set of processing units that interconnects all the information for processing. This model can solve many difficult prediction problems.

RNN: It is also one kind of neural network. Here, R stands for Recurrent. It is a deep learning algorithm for sequential data. It can process many inputs that are sequential and stays at the same state while processing the next serial input. The main difference between a traditional neural network and RNN is that a traditional network processes an input then jumps to the next input where RNN retains the state.

LSTM: Long short-term memory of neural networks is a version of RNN that employs a combination of special and standard units. The LSTM network is well known in the field of deep learning. For time-series data, it is very essential. It can classify, process, and make predictions based on time series data. Since it is variation of RNN, it also proliferates ahead, it processes data and passes on information. There are some differences between the two operations. This difference gives the permission to store or forget information.

E. Compatible Web App

After storing data in the cloud, we must retrieve it from the IoT cloud in order to display it in an understandable manner. This is how a human can easily comprehend what is happening to the livestock at the appropriate time. We can send data to the IoT cloud via the IoT device and display it in real-time on the web. Essentially, the web is used to facilitate the visualization of data. That is why users can easily comprehend. We can visualize the data using the chart. In the modern era, we have a variety of data types that display data in a variety of ways. There is no need to set up a back-end server for IoT compatible web applications because we can retrieve data from the cloud and display it in the front end. As a result, the user can view the information. We simply convert data

to information. We spend considerable time interacting with a user-friendly website. We can use the web to notify users of an emergency situation, allowing them to take appropriate action. Additionally, users specify unique requirements, which the web satisfies. We can compare data to similar cases in the past and provide critical information. Figure 2 depicts the use cases of proposed system.

IV. FUTURE WORK

In the future, several portions of the proposed methods need to be developed to imply complete farm management and prediction systems. At first, all total input factors that are exploited in this article need to be implemented utilizing low-power sensing technology. Hence processing components with networking capabilities and sensor integration is crucial. Another local fog device with high-speed networking and proposed encryption will be employed with SDN to straighten undesirable requests. From the server-side appropriate load balancing algorithms need to be developed to accumulate and accommodate a large amount of generated data. Pre-processing and data extraction steps will be developed to create relevant data-sets. Then these data-sets will be operated on multiple custom-created machine learning and deep learning models for health monitoring, disease, pregnancy, meat, and milk prediction. The whole system will be wrapped in a web application framework. Again all the communication will be encrypted utilizing AES and filtered with SDN.

V. CONCLUSION

For the betterment of animal-based production, the LMS (Livestock Monitoring System) has been introduced to current farming techniques. The LMS has numerous functions, including animal health monitoring, disease tracking, daily milk production, meat intake monitoring, pregnancy prediction, and regular immunization. Farmers may simply observe the current state of the animal using these criteria, and then

categorize their next steps to avoid detrimental influences. In order to improve animal-based productivity, the LMS has been introduced to current farming techniques. The LMS will be implemented with numerous functions, including animal health monitoring, disease tracking, daily milk production, meat intake monitoring, pregnancy prediction, and regular immunization. Farmers may simply observe the current state of the animal using these criteria, and then categorize their next steps to avoid detrimental influences. Moreover, the security is also major concern. Hence, we will encrypt data before sending data to the software defined network.

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